

VOCAL - CHOIR SKILLS AND THEIR SIGNIFICANCE IN THE MUSIC LESSON

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Annotation: This article is about vocal and choir singing in class, ensemble, singing breath, sound formation, tuning, pronunciation, skills, methods of effective organization of students in classes, methods and structure of forming music culture in the minds of students in music classes. detailed.

Keywords: music lesson, interest, task, work, spirituality, vocal, voice, student, analysis, methodology, tradition, education, attention.

The attention paid at the state level to the development of national culture in the construction of a new Uzbekistan is of great importance. In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan According to Sh. Mirziyoev, “The level of development of our people is assessed primarily by our national culture. In this sense, culture is the image of our people, our society. As we begin to create a new image of Uzbekistan, we must begin with the development of our national culture.”[1].

The Uzbek Center for the Study of Cultural Heritage Abroad and the Center for New History of Uzbekistan are being set up. Great attention is paid to the development of reading culture, culture and art, and creative schools and centers named after our great artists are being established in the regions. Systematic measures are being taken to further popularize folklore and amateur arts, and to develop innovative areas of culture and the arts. In this regard, President Shavkat Mirziyoev said, “If culture and art do not develop in the country, society will not develop. It is important to develop the field of culture and arts, to increase the prestige of the Uzbek national culture and art in the world, to realize the potential of young talents. Indeed, when art and culture live, the nation and the people, the whole of humanity, live in peace”.[2]

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 “ On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom”, August 26, 2018 Resolution No. PD - 3920 “ On measures for innovative development of the arts ”, Resolution No. PD-4038 of November 28, 2018 “ On approval of the Concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan”, 2019 Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the

Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1019 of December 19, 2019 “ On approval of the Program for improving the activities of museums in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020-2021”, November 23, 2019 Resolution of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 26, 2019 “ On approval of the activities of the Erkin Vakhidov Memorial Museum and the Treasury House-Museum” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 630 [3] of May 30, 2019 “ On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay ”, “Shakhrisabz”, “Termez” and “ Kokand ” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [4] , 2020 “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [5], 2020 “On measures to further enhance the role and influence of the arts in society” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 325 of June 9, 2021 and “Martyrs’ Memory” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 357 of February 2, 2022 “On support of the Moat Fund” The normative legal acts adopted, such as Resolution No. PD – 1 2 of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan [6] are becoming increasingly important.

Singing in a choir is a complex psychological and physiological process. Vocal-choir work in music culture classes is the most active form of teaching students in moral and aesthetic education. Singing in a choir strengthens students' attention, develops their memory, speech, expands their voice range, increases their musical learning, the period of mutation passes easily, and their worldview is formed year by year. Vocal and choral skills are important in music lessons. Especially during choir lessons, students’ attention, awareness and activity increase, their musical memory develops well, and they feel pleasure when performing the songs they have learned. When singing, creative performance cooperation increases and unites into a friendly team. With the help of vocal and choral skills, students deeply understand the meaning of the words and the melody of the song and learn about life through the content of the work. In order to achieve the above-mentioned results, it is necessary to develop the following vocal and choral skills and strictly adhere to them when singing in a choir. Because it is possible to achieve a pleasant and melodious, pure choral sound only with the help of vocal - choral skills. Vocal-choir skills are divided into 6 (six) types:

1. The situation of singing in class.
2. Breath of anger.
3. Sound generation.

4. Adjustment.
5. Ensemble.
6. Pronunciation.

1. The state of singing. Singing position refers to the position of the students when they sing while sitting or standing. It is necessary to explain to the students how to hold the head, hands and feet when singing while sitting or standing, and to constantly monitor and remind them. The rules of this skill are to stand straight without bending the body, not to lean on the back of the desk while singing, to relax the shoulders, not to raise the chin too much, to hold the neck and head correctly, to lower the hands freely and it means sitting without bending over with palms lightly on the knees and singing freely with feet shoulder width apart.

2. Breath of singer. It is known that there is a certain difference between breathing in singing and physiological breathing. Physiological breathing is natural from birth to the end of a child's life. Breathing in chanting, depending on the character of the song, happens quickly and in short intervals. Inhalation and exhalation are extended depending on the length of the song's sentence, tempo and expression of the character. Artificial respiration is used by actors, singers and singers. It is also called artificial, i.e. breath taken according to need, singing breath. There are the following types of breathing: chest breathing, diaphragmatic breathing, abdominal breathing. Since the chest breath of small children is still narrow and short, they take breath with their chest, so it is natural for them to raise their shoulders, rush, and break up the sentence and word of the song when they sing. Therefore, it is necessary to teach children to breathe calmly without raising their shoulders and to bring it to the end of the sentence of the song, especially not to take a breath in the middle of the word. In the process of working on breathing skills, children's attention is drawn to the strong, smooth, pleasant sound of voices. For this, it is taught to breathe calmly and noiselessly, as if smelling a flower. In the implementation of this qualification, it is formed in practical exercises such as singing vocal-choir exercises recommended in textbooks and manuals, listening to songs performed in children's choirs through magnetic tapes. When children sing exercises and songs, they get used to breathing according to the teacher's hand gestures, and saving it, bringing it to the end of the sentence with rasamati. Conducting situations are especially important for planning the breath of teaching to sing, observing "attention", "auf", "start performance", "end performance". Taking into account the capacity of children's breathing, breathing areas in exercises and

songs are determined in advance, and they are implemented in the process of teaching songs.

3. Sound generation. Voice formation is a complex psychological and physiological process. It is formed by the joint operation of the vocal apparatus (larynx, larynx) and two cone-shaped sound membranes inside it, breathing (lungs, trachea, chest) and hearing apparatus. The sound produced in the throat is weak and raspy, and the vibration of its speech apparatus increases, especially through the nasal cavity, and it has a characteristic timbre and sonority. The sound set to a musical tone in the interaction of the four organs - breath, voice, speech and hearing apparatus - is called singing voice. In the 1st grade, the primary (sol1 - lya1) for students to sing without straining their voice is the working range (mi1 - si1). The general range is (pe1 - do2), which should be followed in moderation. Children sing in a voice close to the faltet based on the head resonator. When making children sing, you should only start with a soft start, never start a song with a hard start. The teacher must supervise this.

4.Adjustment. Soz means that each child clearly perceives the sound of the given music and sings his voice according to it, keeping the melody in his memory. In other words, tuning means singing a sound of a certain pitch with a certain intonation. This is an important skill, because one of the main goals of elementary vocal-choir work is to achieve pure unison. Therefore, from the first lesson, systematic work is carried out on the development of adjustment skills in children. Special attention is paid to children whose music studies are developing slowly. They are encouraged to join the teacher's voice to the sound of musical instruments and the voice of gifted children, and to equalize with the volume, that is, equalize. Intonation pure tone is achieved and is performed through exercises that are sung at the same pitch.

5.Ensemble. Ensemble. - is a French word that means together. It is one of the laws of the arts of music, ballet, and architecture. In music, the joint performance of several performers is called an ensemble. For example, an ensemble of Uzbek folk musical instruments, a dance ensemble, a vocal ensemble, etc. In the chorus, the harmony of all the singers, tempo of performance, rhythm - method and dynamic harmony is called a vocal - choral ensemble. The ensemble is divided into private and general types. When all the performers in the choir tune in to one voice, they all become an ensemble and sing in two or three voices, it is called a general ensemble. Each voice is played separately and the ensemble is called a private ensemble. Harmonization of music and ensemble requires a long work process, and only then can we achieve pure unison, which is the main goal.

6. Pronunciation – singing pronunciation is different from speaking pronunciation. Pronunciation in singing is carried out through active coordination of the organs of articulation (lips, tongue, jaw). Children’s speech is characterized by weakness, indistinctness, and shouting in the choir as a result of straining the vocal apparatus. It is necessary to pay attention to such children and conduct exercises with them individually for a long time, teach them to speak and sing freely without hurrying. It is necessary to learn how to take a breath and finish the sentence by lengthening the vowels and singing the consonants slowly and piece by piece. In this case, it is necessary to pay great attention to the shape of the mouth, the movements and changes of the tongue. The most important thing is to teach children to pronounce the text of exercises and songs according to vocal styles.

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